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Cultivating Community Bonds: A Comprehensive Exploration of Fostering Engagement through Clean Up Drives and Community Gardens in San Jose Rosario Batangas

Aurea M. Gajon, PhD
Teacher III

*Leon M. Manigbas Elementary School
Batangas*

Abstract

This study is being conducted to investigate the impact of clean up drives and community gardens as avenues for fostering community engagement that allows to understand the intricate connections between environmental, social and personal dimensions. The outcome of the study may be a great help to all teachers who wanted to extend their work in the community. The action plan included will be equipped with confidence and proper attitudes. It is conducted during the school year 2022-2023.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the key factors that influence individual's motivation to participate in clean up drives and community gardens?
2. To what extent do clean up drives and community gardens contribute to the development of the community?
3. What is the designed program to improve the implementation of the project?

This study was limited to twenty (20) parents. Data was gathered utilizing the research tool survey. The study was limited in the sense that it only involved participants in one community where the researcher lives.

The study used the descriptive method. The questionnaire was the main instrument used in data gathering. The responses of the study were treated and analyzed using the Frequency and Percentage and Weighted Mean.

Based on the findings, the study revealed that the factors that influence individual's motivation to participate in the activity demonstrated that majority of the parents chose environmental concern which ranked 1 at 30%. It was by health and well being ranked 2 at 25%, Ranked 3 or 20% in community improvement. It was also evident that social interaction and civic engagement were both ranked 4.5 at 10. Stakeholders collaboration was ranked 6.

As to the extent that clean up drives and community gardens contribute to the development of the community demonstrated that was truly effective in the development of the community. Among ten items, seven of them showed a very effective

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verbal interpretation and only three showed an effective verbal interpretation. This means that community see the importance of the project.

To improve the implementation of the project. The researcher designed a program entitled Project SAMBISIG (Samahan ng mga Mamamayang bukas ang isip sa pagkakapitbisib sa pagbangon sa Pandemya). Through this project 100% of the residents enhance and promote their health and quality of life.

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